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Research Article

**THE RELATIONSHIP OF SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS
WITH ANEMIA IN CHILDREN UNDER 3 YEARS OF AGE**Maria Zamurad Khan, Maimoona Zamurad Khan, Mahrukh Ikhlas
Mayo Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Little is known about the prevalence of anaemia and associated factors in school children. In this cross-sectional study, we aimed to determine the prevalence of anaemia and its subtypes, and the associations of types of anaemia with demographic, socio-economic and anthropometric factors among 6–9-year-old primary school children. Haemoglobin (Hb) and mean corpuscular volume (MCV) were measured, and demographic, socio-economic and anthropometric data were collected in 893 children from eight primary schools. The prevalence of anaemia (Hb < 115 g/L) was 12.9% (95% CI: 8.1%, 19.9%), microcytic anaemia (Hb < 115 g/L and MCV < 80 fL) was 7.9% (95% CI: 5.3%, 11.6%) and normocytic anaemia (Hb < 115 g/L and MCV 80–90 fL) was 5.3% (95% CI: 2.9%, 9.5%). No child presented with macrocytic anaemia (Hb < 115 g/L and MCV > 90 fL). Children who were underweight, wasted, or in anthropometric failure (either underweight, stunted or wasted) were more likely to be anaemic (all $p \leq 0.004$), and specifically, to have normocytic anaemia (all $p \leq 0.006$), than those who were not underweight, wasted or in anthropometric failure. Stunted children were more likely to be anaemic ($p = 0.018$) than those who were not stunted. Overweight/obese children were less likely to be anaemic ($p = 0.026$) or have normocytic anaemia ($p = 0.038$) compared with children who were not overweight/obese. No anthropometric status indicator was associated with the risk of microcytic anaemia. No demographic or socio-economic factor was associated with any type of anaemia. Anaemia remains a public health issue in rural areas, and future approaches for its prevention and control should target undernourished primary school children.

Keywords: Anaemia, childhood overweight/obesity, malnutrition, double burden of diseases, school children

Corresponding author:Maria Zamurad Khan,
Mayo Hospital Lahore

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INTRODUCTION:

Anaemia is used as an indicator of nutritional and health status in children because of its adverse effects on childhood morbidity and mortality. Anaemia reportedly causes 600,000 child deaths in low- and middle-income countries annually, with the highest proportion of deaths occurring in South Asia. It is not only a risk factor for impaired physical activity performance and school participation in children, but it may also persist into adulthood. Anaemia in adulthood may lead to negative economic consequences because it has been shown to result in low productivity due to reduced work capacity. Chronic inflammatory disorders, parasite infections, malaria, genetic haemoglobin disorders and co-existing micronutrient deficiencies of iron, folic acid, vitamin B12, and vitamin A play a role in the occurrence of anaemia. Of these, iron deficiency is often assumed to be a major cause of anaemia. Lower age, male sex, lower maternal education, and lower household income have been associated with increased risk of anaemia in childhood. Therefore, effective strategies to prevent and control anaemia must not only rely on understanding the causes of the condition, but must also determine how these may affect vulnerable population groups. Children in low-income countries are particularly at risk of anaemia because their intake of readily bioavailable haem iron from flesh foods is often inadequate in relation to their requirements for growth. Additional exacerbating factors may include malabsorption from gastrointestinal diseases and excessive iron losses (for example during hookworm infection, or malaria). Undernutrition has also been shown to be associated with anaemia in children.

Recently, children with greater adiposity have been shown to be at risk of anaemia because of their higher risk of micronutrient deficiencies such as iron, vitamin A, or zinc, and increased hepcidin concentration due to chronic inflammation in

RESULT:**Correlation and significance of variables studied**

Variables	Coefficient of Correlation R	P Value
Weaning	0.046	0.653
Breast feeding duration	-0.128	0.206
Father's education	0.273	0.006
Father's income	0.227	0.026
Mother's education	0.248	0.013
Mother's income	0.0140	0.1660
No. Of siblings	0.201	0.044
Weight at birth	0.252	0.011
Anemia history	0.304	0.002

overweight/obese children, leading to decreased iron absorption. While iron deficiency can be attributed to approximately half of all anaemia cases, it is more frequent in overweight/obese children compared with normal weight children. To date, limited research has investigated the association between anaemia and childhood overweight/obesity. Studies in overweight/obese children have mainly concentrated on iron deficiency, a single cause of anaemia.

- Pakistan national survey reported that 65% of children between 7-60 months were anemic.[1]
- Different studies have reported prevalence of 70% and 78% in 6-60 months old children in urban squatter settlements in Karachi. [2]

OBJECTIVE:

To find out the association of different socio-demographic factors with anemia in children under 3 years of age.

Operational Definition:

Hemoglobin levels of less than 11 gm/dl was taken as Anemia. [3]

MATERIAL & METHODS:

Study design: Cross-Sectional Study.

Setting: • Mayo Hospital Lahore

Sample size :100

Data collection: Interview based questionnaire.

Data analyzing procedure: SPSS Version 20.

Time Duration: June 2019 to May 2020.

Inclusion Criteria:

Children having age > 6 months and < 3 years along with their recent CBC's reports.

Exclusion Criteria:

Children having blood loss history, blood disorders & congenital anomalies were excluded from the study.

Children who have been brought up by caretaker other than mother.

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF DIET OF CHILDREN PER WEEK

S. NO.	DIET	MEAN± S.D
1.	RED MEAT	3.33 ± 1.045
2.	CHICKEN	3.04 ± 0.737
3.	LEGUMES(LENTILS/BEANS)	3.11 ± 0.931
4.	VEGETABLES	2.93 ± 1.018
5.	FRUITS	2.62 ± 1.391
6.	WHOLE GRAINS	1.97 ± 1.267
7.	TEA/COFFEE	2.72 ± 1.422

Association of monthly income of child’s father with hemoglobin levels

Graphical Presentation Of Mother’s Education With Hb Levels

CONCLUSION:

Mother's education, Father's income, number of siblings showed significant positive correlation with hemoglobin levels in children under 3 years of age. Previous history of anemia showed negative correlation with hemoglobin levels.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Women should be educated enough to have awareness and information about proper type of food which effects hemoglobin levels.
- Family planning should be promoted to have decreased family size as increase living children would increase sharing of family resources.
- Women of the family should also find jobs to improve their financial status.

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